
A REVIEW OF THE IMPACT OF LAND USE MODIFICATION AND CLIMATE CHANGE ON GROUNDWATER-SURFACE WATER DYNAMICS IN NORTHWESTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Land use modifications and climate change broadly impact groundwater-surface water dynamics in Northwestern Nigeria. This paper discusses how land use and climate change changes affect groundwater and surface water in Northwestern Nigeria. Land use modifications in Northwestern Nigeria, driven by agricultural expansion, urbanisation, and traditional practices, have significantly disrupted groundwater-surface water dynamics, resulting in various alterations of hydrological processes, leading to frequent water shortages, increasing surface runoff, and reducing water infiltration. Climate change worsens these issues by altering rainfall patterns, droughts, and rising temperatures. However, through a detailed desk study, literature review, and data analysis, the paper underscores the importance of continuous monitoring and research in understanding and addressing these issues. Integrating local knowledge is also highlighted as crucial to developing sustainable water management practices. The review further emphasises the need for effective strategies to deal with the combined effects of land use changes and climate change. Implementing sustainable land and climate-resilient water management practices incorporating local knowledge and technological innovations is crucial for ensuring long-term water security and resilience in Northwestern Nigeria.

Keywords: Land Use, Groundwater, Surface water, Climate Change, Northwest, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Northwestern Nigeria, land use modification is a significant driver of water stress, surface water contamination, and groundwater depletion (Efe-Jeffery et al., 2024). Land use modifications involve the transformation of the natural landscape or using land, especially for economic activities (Bimal et al., 2017). Land use and climate change play a critical role in groundwater-surface water interactions (Warku & Abera., 2023), and these interactions take place through the replenishing of surface water by groundwater seepage, the loss of surface water to groundwater, or the combination of both (Haris et al., 2019). Therefore, any effect on groundwater or surface water quality or quantity typically affects each other (Winter et al., 1998).

Climate change is worsening the water resource condition in Northwestern Nigeria, where surface and groundwater sources are depleting at unprecedented rates (Salihu & Aishetu., 2022). The impacts of climate change in the Northwestern region of Nigeria are leading to changes in rainfall patterns, increased frequency of droughts, and shrinking water bodies (Owonikoko & Momodu, 2020).

The Northwestern region of Nigeria, a part of the six geopolitical zones of the country, includes states such as Kano, Kaduna, Katsina, Sokoto, Zamfara, Kebbi, and Jigawa (Quadri & Opeyemi, 2021). These states have a rich history of being important agricultural centres, contributing significantly to Nigeria's food production and economy (Amos et al., 2022). The climate is predominantly semi-arid, with distinct wet and dry seasons (Ekpoh & Imo, 2011). The region covers 212,350 km² (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017) and is located between latitudes 08°59'58.5"N to 13°52'39.5"N and 03°28'25.6"E to 10°36'10.2"E (Figure 1). Rainfall in the region is typically concentrated between May and September, with an annual precipitation of 500 mm (Olaniran, O., 2007). According to the National Bureau of Statistics, the region represents 23.338% of Nigeria's total land area (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). Aside from the agricultural strength of the North-west Nigeria region, the region is also known for having the highest fertility rates in the developing world (Bertoni et al., 2016). According to the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) conducted in 2018, the report indicated that the total fertility rate in the northwestern part of Nigeria was 6.6 live births per woman, with an average of 8.3 births for women aged 40 to 49 years in their reproductive lifetimes (NPC and IPF, 2018). The region's population has been proliferating, and this has caused an increased demand for land and water resources (Adegboyega Adeniran et al., 2021). Population growth in Nigeria is also as urban as it is local. Nigeria will have a population of about 229 million in 2024, and demographic projections indicate that the population might experience a constant increase in the following decades, with a population growth of over 377 million people by 2050 (Doris, 2023). DeFries et al. (2010) opine that just as population growth affects rural demand for agriculture and water, the steady growth of the urban population will directly fuel the economic drive to increase agricultural productivity, thereby leading to significant land-use modifications. Understanding the climate status and land use information in northwestern Nigeria is paramount for human and natural resource development (E.M. Okon et al., 2021). However, this region presents a concrete example of a data-poor region (Sedano et al., 2020). Land use change processes combined with the growing impacts of climate change not only compromise household livelihood strategies but also significantly increase the stress on the groundwater-surface water dynamics in the region (Sedano et al., 2020).

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria Showing the Northwest Region (Danibrahim et al., 2022).

2. METHODOLOGY

Selection Criteria and Search Strategy

The methodology employed for this review involved a desk study and a literature review approach. We conducted a comprehensive search across prominent academic databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and Web of Science, utilizing a combination of keywords including "land use change," "Northwestern Nigeria," "groundwater dynamics," "surface water dynamics," "climate change impacts," and "sustainable land management." The inclusion criteria prioritized studies addressing the challenges of Northwestern Nigeria's hydrology and land use modification. The screening and selection process encompassed evaluating titles, abstracts, and full-text content, followed by data extraction and synthesis to organize findings into thematic categories based on predefined research objectives: 1. To analyze historical land use patterns and recent modifications in Northwestern Nigeria. 2. To assess the impacts of climate change on the region's water resources. 3. To explore the interactions between groundwater and surface water under changing environmental conditions, and 4. To identify the implications of these changes for sustainable water management and agricultural practices. The exclusion criteria were as follows: (1) studies that did not relate to the impact of land use or climate change on groundwater-surface water interactions, (2) studies published in languages other than English.

Data Sources and Methods of Analysis

Data was extracted from the selected studies using a standardised approach. The data extracted included study location, land use types or change scenarios, hydrologic response variables measured, and methods used to measure hydrologic response.

Limitations and Potential Biases

We are aware of certain limitations and potential biases in our review process:

Our search method might not have identified all relevant studies, and our criteria for including or excluding studies could have unintentionally excluded some pertinent ones.

1. Differences in how studies were designed and measured may affect how comparable their results are.
2. The findings may not be broadly applicable due to the specific periods covered by the studies we reviewed.
3. Biases related to which studies get published and which languages might have influenced our selection.

To address these issues, we implemented a thorough search strategy and clearly defined criteria for study inclusion. Each study included in our review was carefully assessed for quality and relevance. We also acknowledge potential biases in our interpretation of the results, demonstrating our commitment to transparent and unbiased reporting.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

HISTORICAL LAND USE PATTERNS IN NORTHWESTERN NIGERIA

Traditional agricultural practices in Northwestern Nigeria have given way to more intensive farming methods and have resulted in substantial deforestation rates to make way for agricultural expansion (Sedano et al., 2020). Peter Kojo Boateng (2017) observed that traditional agricultural practices, pastoralism, and small-scale subsistence farming characterized land use patterns in Northwestern Nigeria during the pre-colonial period. The Indigenous communities, including the Hausa and Fulani, practiced shifting cultivation and rotational grazing (Mbih, Richard et al., 2018). Shifting cultivation, also known as slash-and-burn agriculture, involves clearing a piece of land, using it for farming for a few years, and then moving to a new area to allow the old one to regenerate (Stefan et al., 2013). This method was sustainable due to the low population density and the long fallow periods, which allowed the soil to recover its fertility (Mortimore, 1993). The advent of British colonial rule in the early 20th century introduced significant changes to land use patterns (Stephen Olanakanmi, 2021). According to Watts (1983), the colonial administration initiated cash crop farming to integrate the region into the global economy. Crops such as groundnuts (peanuts) and cotton became dominant, replacing some of the traditional food crops. The emphasis on cash crops expanded agricultural land and intensified farming practices (Watts, 1983). The colonial government also implemented land tenure reforms aimed at maximising agricultural production. However, this disrupted traditional land management systems and often led to the marginalisation of pastoralists and small-scale farmers (Scoones, I., 2020). The introduction of railways equally facilitated the transport of agricultural produce to coastal ports for export, further encouraging the cultivation of cash crops (Lugard, 1922).

The post-colonial period marked Nigeria's independence in 1960 and the continued focus on agricultural modernization in the country (Falola et al., 2024). The government implemented policies to promote large-scale farming and mechanisation to achieve food security and economic growth. However, these policies were biased and often favoured large-scale farmers, displacing smallholders and pastoralists. This policy bias further transformed agricultural practices (Emami et al., 2018).

Northwestern Nigeria has experienced rapid population growth and urbanisation in recent decades, further altering land use patterns. The expansion of urban areas has encroached on agricultural land and natural habitats (Aliyu et al.; L., 2017). Additionally, the demand for food and economic pressures have led to the intensification of agriculture, with increased use of irrigation and mechanised farming techniques. These changes have resulted in significant deforestation, soil degradation, and changes in hydrological systems (Sedano et al., 2020).

The study by Sedano et al. (2020), using remote sensing technology, provided detailed insights into the current state of land use in northwestern Nigeria. Their Landsat-based mapping framework revealed that agriculture remains the dominant land use, with arable land covering 52.5% of the area. This data peaks the national average and indicates the extensive agricultural activities in the region. Sedano et al. (2020) further highlighted the prevalence of irrigated agriculture, which is critical for crop production in northwestern Nigeria's arid and semi-arid conditions.

Northwestern Nigeria has evolved to more intensive agricultural systems, and the current landscape indicates extensive agricultural activities and significant environmental changes due to population pressure and urbanisation. Notably, these changes significantly impact water resources in the region (Sedano et al., 2020).

DRIVERS OF LANDUSE CHANGE

Agricultural expansion driven by the need to feed a growing population, as seen in Northwestern Nigeria, can lead to deforestation and the conversion of wetlands (Mfon, Philip et al., 2014). Ogundele et al. (2016) explored the effects of agricultural expansion on groundwater and surface water and inferred that increased agricultural land use reduces the natural infiltration of rainwater into the soil, lowering groundwater recharge rates and increasing surface runoff, and causing soil erosion and sedimentation in water bodies.

Rapid urbanisation drives land use and results in the proliferation of impervious surfaces such as roads, buildings, and pavements (Z. Wang et al., 2020). Studies by M.M. de Sousa et al. (2022) indicated that these surfaces prevent water from infiltrating the ground, reducing groundwater recharge and increasing surface runoff. Sohn et al. (2022) also suggest that urban runoff often carries pollutants, degrading surface water quality and potentially contaminating groundwater. According to observations by R.D. Stewart et al. (2019), urbanisation can influence the impairment of water resources across various levels through increased runoff, water quality issues, flooding risks, hyper-salinization, and loss of aquifer recharge.

The shifting cultivation, also known as the slash-and-burn agriculture pattern, practiced in northwestern Nigeria contributes to the intensification of desertification in the region (Audu & Adie, 2018). Removing forests for agriculture or urban development diminishes the land's capacity to retain and infiltrate water. Trees and vegetation play a crucial role in the water cycle by intercepting rainfall, promoting infiltration, and reducing runoff (Aizebeokhai, 2012).

EFFECTS OF LAND USE CHANGE ON GROUNDWATER-SURFACE WATER DYNAMICS IN NORTHWESTERN NIGERIA

T.A. Woldesenbet et al. (2020) explored the effects of deforestation, urbanisation, and agricultural expansion on groundwater-surface water dynamics and that removing vegetation cover prevents water infiltration into the soil. Without vegetation, rainwater is more likely to

flow over the surface rather than seep into the ground, reducing groundwater recharge and increasing the likelihood of floods (Babaremu et al., 2024). Studies conducted by (Cooley et al., 2021 Huo et al., 2021 and Su et al., 2021) indicate that streamflow patterns of water bodies are also affected by land use (Jorge et al. et al., 2019). For instance, deforestation can lead to higher peak flows during the rainy season and reduced base flows during dry seasons (Hesslerova et al., 2010). These changes are caused by forests acting as natural sponges, absorbing and slowly releasing water. Deforestation affects the capacity of the land to hold, and the gradual release of water diminishes, leading to more erratic streamflow patterns (Da'u et al., 2021). The extensive groundwater use for irrigation in the Northwestern region has led to a decline in groundwater levels. Sedano, Molini, and Azad's (2020) study indicates that nearly 20% of the region's land is under irrigation, significantly stressing groundwater resources. Over-extraction of groundwater lowers the water table, making it more difficult and expensive to access groundwater, and can lead to the depletion of aquifers (Gordon et al., 2010).

According to a review by Mishra et al., 2014, land use changes, particularly the intensification of agriculture, can lead to groundwater contamination. Using fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture can lead to the leaching of nitrates, phosphates, and other chemicals into the groundwater. This contamination risks human health and affects the quality of water available for domestic and agricultural use (Babaremu et al., 2024). Due to deforestation and agricultural expansion, increased surface runoff increases erosion and sedimentation rates in rivers and streams. Sediments can carry nutrients, pesticides, and other pollutants from agricultural fields into surface water bodies, degrading water quality (Gordon et al., 2010). Changes in precipitation patterns and increased temperatures due to climate change can worsen the effects of land use on water resources. For example, reduced rainfall and higher evaporation rates can further stress groundwater and surface water systems already impacted by land use changes (IPCC, 2014). Land use changes can also contribute to climate change, creating feedback mechanisms affecting water dynamics. For example, deforestation leads to the release of carbon stored in trees, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and global warming, influencing water availability and distribution (Bonan, 2008).

CLIMATE CHANGE AND GROUNDWATER-SURFACE WATER DYNAMICS

Studies from (Amjath-Babu et al., 2016; Adeniran et al., 2021) suggest that the increasing demands for groundwater in Northwestern Nigeria, propelled by population growth, urban expansion, agricultural intensification, and industrialisation, frequently outgrow the natural replenishment processes—Nigeria's Northern region experience a decline in water availability and grazing fields (Gürsoy, 2024). The IPCC study using climate models reports projected changes in the amount and distribution of rainfall, leading to more erratic and unpredictable weather patterns (IPCC, 2014). These changes cause decreased rainfall and increased rainfall intensity. Ernest Benjamin Ikechukwu Ugwu (2023) stated that evidence suggests a long-term decline in rainfall in the Sahel and Sudan regions of Northwestern Nigeria. Reduced rainfall decreases surface water availability and limits the recharge of groundwater aquifers, resulting in water scarcity, particularly during the dry season, and affecting agricultural activities and water supply for domestic use (Hong Wang et al., 2015).

In the case of increased rainfall intensity, when rainfall does occur, it is often more intense, leading to higher surface runoff and less infiltration into the soil (Wilk Sampaio et al., 2021). Intense rainfall can also cause flash floods, quickly carrying water away before it can percolate into the ground, thus reducing groundwater recharge (Nnaji et al., Nnennaya., 2014). Rising temperatures due to climate change increase the rate of evapotranspiration, the process

by which water is transferred from the land to the atmosphere through evaporation and plant transpiration (Abteu et al., Assefa, 2013). Higher temperatures can significantly affect both surface and groundwater resources through increased evaporation rates from surface water bodies, reducing the volume of surface water available for various uses (Chen et al., Qi., 2004), and by depletion of soil moisture, which is crucial for recharging groundwater (Kumar, C.P., 2003).

The combined effects of altered precipitation and increased evapotranspiration contribute to the declining groundwater levels in Northwestern Nigeria Ashaolu (Eniola & Iroye, Kayode., 2018). Omole, David (2013) studied groundwater levels in Northwestern Nigeria and observed that groundwater levels declined in many parts of the region, partly due to reduced recharge rates and increased abstraction for agricultural and domestic use. Wilby, Robert (2009) stated that climate change affects not only groundwater but also the availability and dynamics of surface water. Alterations in flow regimes due to changes in rainfall patterns and increased evaporation rates can disrupt the balance of hydrologic systems and affect the livelihoods of communities dependent on riverine resources (Ayoade, 1975).

Climate change and land use have a combined effect. Climate change can exacerbate the hydrological impacts of land use modifications. The interaction of these two factors can increase runoff and decrease groundwater recharge in the Northwestern Nigeria region (M.L. Tan, 2021).

Comprehensive and up-to-date data on land use, groundwater levels, and surface water quality in Northwestern Nigeria must be improved. Continuous monitoring and interdisciplinary studies are required. Regardless, there has been significant progress in related studies. Land use modifications in Northwestern Nigeria, driven by agricultural expansion, urbanisation, and traditional practices, have significantly disrupted groundwater-surface water dynamics. However, the long-term impacts of current land use practices and climate change on water resources remain unclear, highlighting the need for longitudinal research.

Climate change has worsened the issues in the region. Unprecedented precipitation patterns, increasing drought frequency, and rising temperatures sporadically intensify water scarcity and stress in the region. Land use modification and climate change have a combined effect. For all impacts of land-use modification on groundwater and/or surface water, climate change ripples the speed of these impacts and hinders the region from adjustment and development.

Despite the current progress and the importance of the situation, effective mitigation and adaptation strategies to address these combined impacts are under-researched. However, there is a significant potential for positive change. By increasing the engagement of local communities and incorporating Indigenous knowledge in water management practices, we can make significant strides in addressing these issues. This potential for positive change should inspire hope and motivation in our collective efforts.

4. CONCLUSION

The interplay between land use modifications and climate change in Northwestern Nigeria has profoundly disrupted groundwater-surface water dynamics and worsened water scarcity and quality issues. Available research shows that how land is used and reused in the region has contributed to the hydrological system's stress. Whatever the effects, climate change worsens the condition and impact range and makes adaptation and mitigation efforts futile or burdensome. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive data collection and

interdisciplinary research. It also involves the development of climate resilient-sustainable land and water management practices that incorporate local community involvement and technological innovations in the region.

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